

The Influence of Self-Control and Conformity on Impulse Purchases of Cosmetic Products in Women

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Abstract.

These day people shopping not only to fulfill needs but also desires which makes someone behaving impulsively when they buying something. Self-control and conformity are two things that influence the tendencies of impulsive buying. This study aims to test empirically the effect of self-control and conformity on impulsive buying of cosmetic products in women. This study involved 127 respondents. The sampling technique in this study is purposive sampling and used data analysis techniques in the form of multiple linear regression. The results of the study proved that conformity and self-control jointly influenced women's impulsive buying tendencies.

Keywords: *conformity, self-control, impulsive buying*

Shopping is something that is often done to get the items needed for daily needs, but with the times and the advancement of technology shopping is now easier with online shopping. People tend to shop not only to fulfill their needs but also to follow their desires which makes a person behave impulsively when shopping. The results of the Frontier Consulting Group survey (Zoel, 2012) show that Indonesians tend not to have a regular shopping pattern, do not have a clear record when going shopping, especially most Indonesians will buy goods when the item runs out that day so that the tendency to buy more than they need is higher. This is also supported by the results of Mastercard research written by Primadhyta (2015) in an article on CNN Indonesia which explains from 2,272 young people (millennial generation) respondents in Asia Pacific that 50% of Indonesian young people aged 18-29 years are impulsive consumers in Asia Pacific, and the second most impulsive after Thailand.

According to Bayley and Nancarrow (1998) impulsive buying is shopping behavior that occurs unplanned, due to emotional attraction, where the decision-making process is carried out quickly without thinking wisely and considering all available information and alternatives. impulsive buying usually occurs because of a sudden, often strong, and persistent desire to get an item immediately. Rook (1987).

Loudon and Bitta (1993) say impulsive buying is divided into 4 types, namely, the first, pure impulse buying means that purchases occur without any prior thought or planning to buy. Second, suggestion impulse means purchases made without prior planning. This purchase occurs when someone sees the usage procedure or product. Usually, this purchase is made because of the influence of the seller he meets when shopping, so that he finally decides to make a purchase. Third, reminder impulse means purchase

occurs when consumers are reminded to buy a product outside of their habits, this usually happens because consumers see a brochure or advertisement in a shopping center. Fourth, planned impulse means that purchases are made because they have actually been planned in advance. But when the item in question does not match what is desired, the purchase is made to a similar item but with a different brand or size. In addition, the factors that influence impulsive buying are divided into three (1) Products with low price characteristics, small or marginal needs, short-term products, small sizes, and easily accessible stores. (2) Marketing and marketing which includes distribution in a large number of self-service outlets, advertising through highly suggestible and continuous mass media, advertising at the point of sale, prominent display positions and store locations. (3) Consumer characteristics such as personality, gender, social demographics or socio-economic characteristics. (Loudon and Bitta, 1993).

According to astari and widagda (2014) female consumers are the figure of actors who have a great opportunity to make impulse purchases. When compared to men, regarding women being a figure who has the opportunity to make impulsive buying, one of the products that are in great demand is cosmetics Poerwadarminta (2007) says cosmetics are beauty tools such as powder, cream, and lotion to beautify the skin, hair, and other faces. According to Dona (2013) cosmetics are a necessity

for women. Most of the women, like to spend more money to buy makeup equipment, ranging from powder, eyeshadow, body lotion, to masks. The cost of buying it cannot be said to be cheap. Cosmetics, which are actually secondary items, have become primary needs in the lives of women. Engel (1995) says that women tend to be more influenced by emotionality than rationality. Emotionality has a close relationship with the concept of impulse buying presented by. Women also tend to have a lower ability to control themselves than male consumers so that they are more likely to do impulsive buying. Chaplin (2002) says self-control is the ability to guide behavior self; the ability to suppress or inhibit impulses or impulsive behavior. Meanwhile, Hurlock (1990) says self-control is related to how individuals control emotions and urges within themselves. According to Block and Block (in Ghufon, 2011) there are three types of self-control, the first is over control, which is excessive control and causes a person to control a lot and refrain from reacting to a stimulus. Second, under control, which is the tendency to release free impulses without careful calculation. Third, appropriate control, which is control that allows individuals to control their impus appropriately. In addition, there are three aspects of self-control according to Tangney, Baumeister, & Boone (2004), namely, (1) Breaking Habits or breaking habits is something related to doing behavior outside of the habits he often does. This means that individuals perform behavior that violates the values or norms and regulations that are around them. Individuals with breaking habits are less able to control problems in their drive to be able to comply with the values or norms and regulations around them. (2) Resisting Temptation is something related to an individual's assessment of their self-regulation in resisting temptation. Individuals are able to complete work properly without being influenced by things outside of their duties even though they are fun. Individuals with resisting temptation are able to give their attention to the work being done. (3) Self-Discipline, which refers to the ability that reflects the ability to control oneself. This means that individuals are able to focus on themselves when doing a task or activity. Individuals with self-discipline are able to restrain themselves from other things that can interfere with their concentration.

According to Baron and Byrne (2005) conformity is the adjustment of behavior to adhere to reference group norms, accepting group ideas or rules that govern how to behave. Conformity is seen as

The tendency to allow other people's attitudes and opinions to control themselves (Chaplin, 2002). According to Myers (2012) there are three forms of conformity, (1) acceptance, which is acceptance when individuals act and believe according to social pressure from either individuals or groups. (1) Compliance, which is the fulfillment of conformity to social requests or pressures but individuals do not agree. (3) Obedience, which is compliance to act in accordance with direct orders. Furthermore, Sears, Freedman, & Peplau (2006) state that there are four aspects of peer conformity. The first aspect is trust in the group, which is the individual's belief that all information provided by the group is correct. The second aspect is weak trust in personal thoughts, where individuals do not believe in their abilities, resulting in individuals depending on the group. The third aspect is the fear of being a deviant, which is the individual's desire to be accepted and liked by the environment so as not to look different from the social group. The fourth aspect is the fear of social reproach, which is the feeling of fear that an individual has when different from his group.

The above is supported by several previous studies such as those conducted by Larasati and Budiani (2014), regarding impulse buying and self-control. Which in his research found that there is a relationship between the two variables with a negative relationship direction, this means that the higher the individual's self-control, the lower the impulse purchase. Furthermore. research conducted by Research by Sholikah and Dania (2017) shows that there is a significant positive relationship between peer conformity and impulsive buying behavior. The higher the peer conformity, the higher the impulsive buying behavior. Conversely, the lower the peer conformity, the lower the impulsive buying behavior.

Based on the description of the problem above, the hypothesis of this study is that first, there is an influence of self-control on the tendency to impulse buy cosmetic products in women. And the second is that there is an influence of conformity on the tendency to impulse buy cosmetic products in women.

METHOD

The purpose of this study was to empirically examine the effect of self-control and conformity on the tendency to impulse buy cosmetic products in women. So this study uses a quantitative approach with multiple regression techniques. The subjects in this study were women who were over 18 years old and enjoyed shopping for cosmetics. The sampling method in this study used purposive sampling technique, namely determining the sample with certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2009). Based on data collection, 127 participants were obtained. The data measurement tools needed in this study were obtained using the Likert scale model, by presenting four alternative answers, namely SS (strongly agree), S (agree), TS (disagree), and STS (strongly disagree) which consisted of three scales, namely. conformity scale, self-control scale and impulsive purchase scale of cosmetic products.

Self-control in this study was measured by the Brief self-control Scale compiled by arifin & milla (2020) which is an adaptation of Tangney, Baumeister, & Boone (2004). Based on three aspects of self-control, namely aspects of Breaking Habits, Resisting Temptation and Self-Discipline. This measuring instrument consists of 10 items 3 favorable items and 6 unfavorable items. After going through the calculation of the discrimination power of the items, there were 3 items that were canceled. The number of remaining items becomes 7 items with a range of 0.408-0.770 with Cronbach's alpha of 0.846.

Conformity in this study was measured by the conformity scale compiled by Mehrabian & Stefl (1995) and based on aspects of conformity according to Baron and Byrne (2005), namely normative social aspects and informative social aspects. This measuring instrument consists of 11 items, 7 favorable items and 4 unfavorable items. After going through the calculation of the discrimination power of the items, there are no invalid items with a range of 0.365-0.742 with Cronbach's alpha of 0.847.

Impulsive buying in this study was measured by The Impulse buying tendency scale compiled by Verplanken and Herabadi (2001) based on aspects of impulsive buying, namely cognitive aspects and affective aspects This measuring instrument consists of 20 items, 18 favorable items and 2 unfavorable items. After going through the calculation of the discrimination power of the items, there were 5 items that were canceled. The number of remaining items became 15 items with a range of 0.576-0.888 with Cronbach's alpha of 0.914.

RESULTS

Assumption tes are carried out to determine the normality and linearity of the data. Based on normality testing on the self-control scale, the significance result is 0.002 ($\rho < .05$), this means that the self-control scale has an abnormal score distribution, then on the confromity scale the significance result is 0.000 ($\rho < .05$), which means that the confromity scale has an abnormal score distribution. Meanwhile, the impulsive buying scale obtained a significance of 0.051 ($\rho > .05$) which means that the impulsive buying scale has a normal score distribution. In the linearity test, all independent variables, namely self-control and self-confidence with impulse buying, are linear with a significance of 0.003 ($\rho < .05$). The results can be seen in table 1.

Table 1. Normality Test Results

Variable	Kolmogorov-Smirnov	P	Description
<i>self-control</i>	0.002	($\rho < .05$)	Abnromal
<i>conformity</i>	0.000	($\rho < .05$)	Abnormal
<i>impulsive buying</i>	0.051	($\rho > .05$)	Normal

This study aims to examine the effect of self-control and conformity on the tendency to impulse buy cosmetic products in women. Based on the results of multiple regression, it is found that the significance result is 0.06 on the confromity variable with impulse buying, which means that there is an influence of conformity on the tendency to impulse buy cosmetic products in women. These results are in

line with previous research The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Bhakuni (2013) entitled A Study on The Effect of Impulsivity and Conformity Behavior on Impulse Buying Behavior of Students and get the results of the study. That conformity has an influence on impulse buying. In addition, the significance result of 0.238 was also obtained on the self-control variable with impulsive purchases, which means that there is an influence of self-control on the tendency to impulse buy cosmetic products in women. Which is in accordance with previous research entitled the relationship between self-control and consumptive behavior of online shopping for fashion products in medical faculty students of Sam Ratulangi University class of 2011 by Chita, David & Pali (2015) which found that there is a relationship between self-control and consumptive behavior. The results can be seen in table 2.

Table 2.

Variable	sig.
<i>self-control</i>	0.238
<i>Conformity</i>	0.06

These results prove that both hypotheses in this study are accepted. With an R square value of 0.091, this means that self-control and conformity together affect impulsive buying tendencies by 9.1%, while the remaining 90.9%. determined by other variables outside the variables of conformity and self-control. The results can be in table 3.

This is supported by previous research entitled The effect of purchasing situation and conformity behavior on young students impulse buying by Wu and Huan (2016) which states that conformity is one of the factors that influence impulse buying, but not the main factor.

Table 3.

Variable	R²	Adjusted R²
Self-control & Conformity	0.90	0.75

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the research results that have been obtained, it can be concluded that conformity and self-control together have an effect on impulse buying tendencies in women. Conformity and self-control independently also affect impulsive buying tendencies in women. It is also known that self-control and conformity together affect impulsive buying tendencies by 9.1% while the remaining 90.9% is determined by other variables outside the variables of conformity and self-control.

Suggestions for women who have a tendency to make impulsive purchases, are expected to increase self-control over decisions before buying something and are expected to consider which items are really needed to buy not just follow the surrounding environment.

For future researchers, it is hoped that researchers can improve the quality of research, starting with data collection with more in-depth interviews and also refining impulse buying items, self-control, and conformity, besides that further researchers are also expected to examine other factors of impulse buying.

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